

THE USE OF GRAMMATICAL GAMES IN THE ELEMENTARY GRADES TO IMPROVE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF NATIVE LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article will talk about the use of grammatical games in the lessons of “Mother Tongue and reading literacy” in primary education. It also shows the methodological aspects of organizing grammatical games.*

Keywords: *elementary education, native language and reading literacy, grammatical play, creative thinking, resourcefulness, activity, efficiency.*

In our country, huge reforms are being carried out in the field of Education. We are not mistaken if we say that the implementation of the subject “mother tongue and reading literacy” in primary education is the result of these reforms. Special attention is paid to the orientation of students towards independent and creative thinking in the lessons of “mother tongue and reading literacy”. In the national curriculum and textbooks created on its basis, the goal is to abandon the memorization of grammatical rules, to form a creative mindset, to focus lessons and classes on the development of students' speech skills. The following main goal stands before the education of the mother tongue: the training of the mother tongue should be aimed at the formation and development of skills for the correct, fluent expression of the product of creativity, independent thinking, creative thought in children in oral and written forms in accordance with the speech situation. Consequently, learning the mother tongue is a great aha in teaching, educating and developing a child.

The leading linguistic principle of learning the native language of primary classes is the study of all aspects of the language in a coherent way.

And the main task of teaching the mother tongue in elementary grades is to master the knowledge system of this discipline, develop grammatical forms of words, form a literate writing skill. The realization of these tasks is extremely complex, requiring the teacher to master various teaching techniques, to teach students to think creatively as much as possible.

Elementary students reflect primarily through imagination. The laws and regulations of the native language, the phenomena of which dictate abstract reasoning. Thanks to this, they often strive to play, to act physically. Based on the current curriculum, game training is often found in the construction of today's lessons. Because the absorption of the knowledge given to the child by the means of games seems more interesting than memorizing the dry rule and training the chronic, and allows the mentioned topic to be firmly remembered. Educational games, especially used in elementary school mother tongue and reading literacy classes, increase students' cognitive activity, prevent mental fatigue. There are several types of educational games, one of which is grammatical games.

Grammatical games help to overcome difficulties in teaching language materials. These games are carried out taking into account the age characteristics of children. Grammatical games

promote independence in children. Encourages students to think quickly, respond independently, be mindful, take initiative in every endeavor. It also brings together the attention of the children while encouraging grammar games to function. Gives birth to a healthy competitive spirit in students. These games require students to be active, resourceful, understanding, able to put into practice the theoretical knowledge gained during the course of the lesson.

Morphological materials are studied much more widely in the elementary grades. During four years of study, students acquire a certain knowledge of the word and its meanings, word form, morphological composition of the word. Word categories gain theoretical as well as more practical knowledge over its basic, complementary and specific sign.

The primary school mother tongue and reading literacy curricula are structured on the principle of a phased sequence, taking into account the characteristics of students as they grow mentally, morally and physically year after year. Based on this, the part of each subject that is easily mastered by students is studied in the lower grades, the more complex part is studied in the later grades. Some word categories are learned in all classes of primary education. The knowledge given to the student is built on the basis of the knowledge received by children in previous classes. This allows you to organize a variety of grammatical games, relying on the previously acquired knowledge of the reader.

In the elementary grades, the word term is used in place of morphology. In this, students learn the similarities and differences of each grammatical phenomenon. By comparing them, different grammatical games can be arranged. Such training can also be used in every lesson devoted to the study of morphology. For example, when crossing horses with a horse, it can be compared with a related horse, and when passing agreement suffixes, it is possible to organize a grammatical game using a two-word-making suffix that is close to each other when the horse-maker learns the suffixes.

We bring examples from some grammatical games that serve to improve the effectiveness of primary class native language education:

The game "**chain of words**". The game requires readers to pay attention to each word, its structural aspect. Any word is taken to pass the game. Whichever sound the chosen word ends with, it is necessary that the next word begins with that sound. Readers will quickly find the desired word and will be able to see the result of their creativity at once. The game can be played between a number of students or among separate groups to be fun.

In order to ensure that the game is productive, it is good to tie it into certain word categories. Students also consolidate their knowledge of a particular word category by performing this game. For example, a game on words that are part of the noun phrase category can be organized as follows: 1. Noun with nouns: Rustam, Muradali, will, Andijan, Navoi, etc. 2. Related nouns: apples, figs, pens, amma, etc.k.

Staging a game with the participation of words that fall into the category of quality words: large, excellent, warm, red, lazy, tyrannical, important, kind, sour, delicate, blue, etc.

These types of games can also be held on topics such as animals, words that express movement, and the cultivation of melons. This game requires a close look at each word, paying special attention to its meaning. This game prepares students to say bahr-u bayt in literature classes in the future.

The game "**find the word right**". In the game, the students of the class are divided into two groups. Children in each group choose from the given text the words regarding the assignment

given by the teacher. For example, readers in the first group selectively write words about the noun phrase category in the text, and those in the second group selectively write words about the adjective word category. To do this, the teacher shows the children a portable board or cardboard with the words written on it. Both groups get to work, whichever group of students does the assignment quickly and correctly-that group is the winner and encouraged.

The game "**Victory peak**". Two students are taken out to the board to play this game. Each of them is given one productive word-making supplement. Students are required to compose a set number of words and write on a board using a given crafting supplement. This game can be organized when the noun, adjective, verb word categories are passed. In the process of studying the noun phrase category, the game can be organized as it should. 1) –poison: apricot, cotton, ... 2) - bear: compatriot, comrade..

The coming of the agreement game. It is performed to study the proper use and application of the game's agreement suffixes and to keep the spelling memorable. Students use the departure and place moment (-to -in), proceeds, and crowbar (-to and -of) to replace the suffix of the agreement. In order to avoid this, a grammatical game is organized as follows. 1. We went to the garden (-in -to). 2. We want to go to work (-in -to). 3. The car (-on -to) is walking. 4. I see that there is a forehead (-in -to). 5. Read (-to -in) you were the first. 6. The village went (-to -in).

The game "**make the necessary word**". The main purpose of this play is to ensure that the grammatical rules are firmly and consciously occupied by the students. Through this game, students acquire the ability to correctly approach the concept that each word represents and use them in their place. 1. Name of the horse. 2. Quality mark. 3. Number Number, order. 4. Verb work-movement.

In the game, students can be given words in the form of a handout, and they can be placed in the above groups.

In conclusion, the importance of grammatical games, such as the one above, is very great in the assimilation of students' knowledge of grammatical concepts in elementary school native language and reading literacy classes. In the process of such a game, students acquire the skills to be able to put into practice the theoretical knowledge they have received.

The organization of grammatical games also requires taking into account a number of methodological factors. When applying this method to the course process, it is necessary for the teacher to take a creative approach to each topic, its content. It is also important that when organizing grammatical games, the characteristics of the students of the class must also be taken into account. The level of assimilation of students, in which class they study and take into account the topics studied and structure the content of training according to these indicators positively affects the effective organization of grammatical games. Allows you to quickly and firmly master the studied grammatical concepts. Grammar games should not be accidental, no matter what section of grammar is passed on. The teacher must carefully prepare for the organization of these games.

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